

From Broken Memory to Digital Archive: Bridging Heritage Preservation and Roots Tourism in Moroccan Jewish Communities Through AI and Computational Onomastics

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Abstract

The Moroccan Jewish diaspora, estimated at 1.2 million individuals worldwide, maintains a deep emotional attachment to its country of origin despite six decades of emigration. This attachment manifests as a persistent identity tension between Moroccan cultural roots and Israeli integration, Haddaji (2025) has documented how this attachment describes a “broken memory” (Malka, 1978) that successive generations risk losing entirely. Ouaknine and Aharony (2020) showed that the primary motivation for participation in online Moroccan heritage communities is memory and culture preservation, and Ouaknine (2023) demonstrated that nostalgia significantly moderates well-being and social network participation among Moroccan Jews and Muslims. Simultaneously, Ouaknine (2026) has developed Yahasra.org, a computational platform documenting 29,977 burial records across 36 Moroccan Jewish cemeteries, applying population genetics methods to surname-based demographic analysis. This paper proposes a framework for bridging the gap between heritage preservation (as documented in the burial database) and roots tourism, using AI-powered tools to transform static archival data into personalized travel experiences. We describe the Zyara heritage trip planner, an AI agent that connects diaspora families to their ancestral communities through surname search, cemetery localization, and itinerary generation. We argue that the convergence of computational onomastics, structured burial databases, and AI-driven trip planning creates a new paradigm for diaspora engagement: one that transforms the nostalgia described by Ouaknine and Aharony (2020) into active, data-driven heritage rediscovery.

Keywords: Moroccan Jewish diaspora, roots tourism, digital heritage, computational onomastics, AI trip planning, cemetery documentation, Sephardic genealogy

Introduction

Victor Malka (1978) titled his study of Moroccan Jews *The Broken Memory*, a phrase that has since become emblematic of the community's relationship to its past. The metaphor captures a fundamental paradox: Moroccan Jews carry an intense attachment to their homeland, yet the material and institutional infrastructure that sustained communal memory (the mellahs, the synagogues, the cemeteries, the oral traditions) is deteriorating or has already been lost. Haddaji (2025) has documented this paradox through interviews with Moroccan Jews who immigrated to Israel in the 1950s and 1960s, describing how “generations of Moroccan Jewish immigrants are disappearing, which will leave future generations disconnected from their Moroccan origins like a tree uprooted from its native soil, content only with nostalgia and stories told within families about the Morocco of yesteryear” (Haddaji, 2025).

This generational erosion is not unique to Moroccan Jewry, but it is particularly acute for several reasons. First, the emigration was rapid and near-total: from approximately 250,000–280,000 Jews in the late 1940s, Morocco's Jewish population fell to a few thousand by the 1970s (Laskier, 1994). Second, as Haddaji (2025) argues, the Zionist project in Israel actively sought to replace Moroccan Jewish identity with a new “Hebrew” identity. Jabotinsky (1926, as cited in Poirier, 1998) explicitly called to “extirpate from the Jews of Eretz Israel all traces of the oriental soul,” creating what Haddaji describes as a “memorial trauma” in which the immigrant's cultural heritage was devalued. Third, the physical sites of memory, particularly the cemeteries, which are the last material link to communities that otherwise left no trace, are subject to weathering, neglect, and in some cases destruction.

Against this background of accelerating loss, two developments offer a path toward preservation and reconnection. The first is the emergence of large-scale digital heritage databases. Ouaknine (2026) has described Yahasra.org, a platform containing 29,977 burial records from 36 Moroccan Jewish cemeteries spanning the period 1690–2026, with a statistical engine implementing Hill number diversity indices, Chao1 richness estimation, isonymy coefficients, and inter-community surname distances. The Chao1 estimator indicates that the database

captures approximately 44% of historical surname diversity, with an estimated 4,381 surnames not yet documented, a finding that simultaneously validates the scale of the effort and quantifies the urgency of continued fieldwork.

The second development is the growth of Jewish heritage tourism in Morocco. Boumeeggouti (2020) has analyzed this phenomenon as a significant niche market, noting that tour operators and private agencies now offer specialized Jewish heritage itineraries including synagogues, cemeteries, mellahs, and the Museum of Moroccan Judaism in Casablanca. Cardeira da Silva (2018) has examined how Moroccan Jewish “first-places” function as sites of pilgrimage and identity reconstruction for diaspora communities. More than 200,000 Jews visit Morocco annually, including 70,000 Israelis who visited Morocco in 2022 following the reestablishment of diplomatic relations under the Abraham Accords (Haddaji, 2025; Bensimon, 1991).

What is missing, however, is a systematic bridge between the structured data in heritage databases and the experiential needs of roots tourists. A family searching for ancestral graves currently has no automated way to query a burial database, locate relevant cemeteries, and generate a culturally informed travel itinerary. This paper proposes such a bridge through the Zyara heritage trip planner, an AI-powered tool accessible at yahasra.org/hackathon/trip-planner, and argues that computational onomastics, structured burial data, and AI-driven personalization can transform passive diaspora nostalgia into active heritage engagement.

The Problem: Memory Without Infrastructure

The erosion of material heritage

Moroccan Jewish cemeteries are the primary remaining material link between diaspora communities and their ancestral homeland. Unlike synagogues, many of which have been converted, demolished, or repurposed, cemeteries contain permanent, inscribed records of names, dates, familial relationships, and communal structure. However, these sites are deteriorating. Ouaknine (2026) notes that “many cemeteries are deteriorating: stones weather, inscriptions become illegible, and sites face encroachment or neglect.” The Chao1 analysis estimates that 56.5% of historical surname diversity remains undocumented, representing families whose traces may be permanently lost if current deterioration continues.

The Moroccan government has undertaken significant restoration efforts (160 Jewish cemeteries have been renovated since 2010) and the 2011 Constitution recognized Jewish heritage as a component of Morocco’s national identity (Boumezzouzi, 2020). However, physical restoration alone does not address the informational challenge: a restored cemetery with legible inscriptions remains inaccessible to a diaspora family in Haifa or Montreal who does not know which cemetery to visit or how to locate a specific grave.

The identity gap

Haddaji (2025) has documented the identity crisis facing Moroccan Jews in Israel with particular clarity. She describes how the Zionist project sought to create “a new unique cultural identity” (Haddaji, 2025) separate from the diaspora, where “the term ‘Jew’ was replaced by ‘Hebrew’ in institutions and surnames, and first and last names also disappeared in favour of biblical names.” The poet Biton Erez captured this tension: “My name’s not Schwartz, I’m Jais, I’m Jais, ana maghribi, I come from the Atlas” (Erez, 1979, as cited in Haddaji, 2025). This is not merely a cultural complaint but a genealogical one: when surnames are changed, transliterated differently, or abandoned, the chain of transmission that connects a living person to an ancestral grave is broken.

This is precisely the problem that computational onomastics can address. Ouaknine (2026) reports that the Yahasra database contains 3,660 distinct surname spellings consolidated into 1,925 canonical forms by the MJPN algorithm (Moroccan Jewish Phonetic Normalization), with an F1 score of 95.5%. A family searching for “Chetrit” can be linked to “Benchetrit,” “Chitrit,” “Shetreet,” and 9 additional variants, all representing the same phonetic family across Hebrew, French, and Arabic transliteration traditions. Without this normalization, the genealogical chain remains broken even when the data exists.

The Bridge: From Database to Journey

Architecture of the Zyara trip planner

The Zyara heritage trip planner (accessible at yahasra.org/hackathon/trip-planner; see Figure 1) is an AI-powered conversational agent designed to transform the Yahasra burial database into a personalized heritage tourism tool. The system operates through four interconnected functions:

Surname search. The user enters a family name. The system queries the Yahasra database using MJPN phonetic normalization (Ouaknine, 2026) to retrieve all matching records across spelling variants and communities. For a surname like “Harroch,” this returns results across 28 known variants including Benarroch, Benharrosh, and 25 others, spanning multiple cemeteries.

Community localization. Matching records are grouped by community, providing the user with a map of ancestral presence. The Location Quotient (LQ) analysis from the statistical engine identifies whether a family was “rooted” (concentrated in a single community over generations) or “dispersed” (present across multiple communities), which directly informs the travel itinerary.

Historical contextualization. For each community, the system provides demographic context drawn from the statistical engine: the temporal distribution of burials, the number of documented families, rabbinical presence, and surname diversity metrics. This transforms a cemetery visit from a passive experience into an informed encounter with communal history.

Itinerary generation. Based on the surname matches, community locations, and practical constraints (travel time, accommodation, Shabbat observance), the AI agent generates a multi-day heritage itinerary connecting relevant cemeteries, mellahs, synagogues, and other sites of Jewish heritage.

Figure 1. The Zyara heritage trip planner interface (yahasra.org/hackathon/trip-planner). Left: welcome screen with database statistics (2,076 Marrakech records, 838 Safi records). Right: personalized family search results for the surname Ouaknine, showing 56 documented family members across spelling variants (Ouaknine, Oiknine, Waknine, Ouaknin), notable individuals, etymological information, and visit recommendations.

From nostalgia to agency

The critical insight is that the trip planner transforms what Haddaji (2025) describes as passive nostalgia, “content only with nostalgia and stories told within families,” into active genealogical agency. This transformation builds on empirical evidence from Ouaknine and Aharony (2020), who found that 75% of participants in Moroccan online heritage communities cited memory and culture preservation as their primary motivation, and from Ouaknine (2023), who demonstrated that among participants with high nostalgia levels, higher well-being contributes to significantly higher social network participation ($B = 0.54$, $p < .001$). The Zyara trip planner channels the nostalgia-driven engagement documented in these studies toward a concrete heritage outcome: the return journey. A second-generation Israeli of Moroccan descent who knows only that “my

grandmother was from somewhere in Morocco” can enter a surname and receive a specific, actionable itinerary linking them to documented graves, dated inscriptions, and community-level demographic context. The system does not replace the emotional dimension of the return journey, which Haddaji’s informants describe as deeply moving, but provides the informational scaffolding that makes such a journey possible for families who have lost the oral transmission chain.

This addresses a gap identified by Boumezzout (2020), who notes that while Jewish heritage tourism in Morocco has grown significantly, it remains largely organized around generic itineraries of major sites (Casablanca, Fez, Marrakech, Essaouira) rather than personalized ancestral reconnection. The trip planner shifts the paradigm from site-based tourism to family-based heritage recovery.

Computational Onomastics as the Connective Tissue

The feasibility of this bridge depends on the ability to reliably connect a living person’s surname to records in a burial database, a task complicated by the multilingual transliteration environment of Moroccan Jewish onomastics. Ouaknine (2026) describes this challenge in detail: a single family name may appear in Hebrew, French, Spanish, and Arabic transliterations, each with multiple orthographic conventions. The MJPN algorithm addresses this by encoding language-specific rules for Hebrew–French–Arabic transliteration patterns, achieving a consolidation ratio of 1.90:1 (3,660 raw spellings to 1,925 canonical forms) and substantially outperforming general-purpose phonetic algorithms (Soundex: 71.4%; NYSIS: 65.1%) on this domain.

The onomastic layer serves a dual function in the heritage tourism context. First, it enables accurate surname matching across transliteration traditions, connecting an Israeli family searching for “Abihssera” to graves inscribed as “Abehserra,” “Abouhassera,” or “Abihssira.” Second, the population genetics metrics computed from the normalized surname data provide contextual information that enriches the tourism experience: a family learning that their surname has an LQ of 88.3 in Debdou (meaning it is overwhelmingly concentrated there) gains a specific geographic anchor for their heritage, while a family whose surname is “dispersed” (LQ < 0.7 across many communities) learns something equally meaningful about their ancestors’ mobility and mercantile or rabbinical networks.

Implications for Heritage Policy and Tourism Development

A data-driven case for fieldwork investment

The Chao1 finding that 56.5% of historical surname diversity remains undocumented (Ouaknine, 2026) provides a quantitative argument for targeted investment in cemetery documentation. Each undocumented surname represents a potential tourist who cannot be connected to their heritage. If even a fraction of the estimated 200,000 annual Jewish visitors to Morocco could be connected to specific ancestral graves through expanded database coverage, the economic case for documentation fieldwork becomes self-reinforcing: more documentation enables more personalized tourism, which generates revenue that can fund further documentation.

Intergenerational transmission

Haddaji (2025) identifies the central threat as generational: “Generations of Moroccan Jewish immigrants are disappearing, which will leave future generations disconnected from their Moroccan origins.” Davis (1977) argued that nostalgia uses the past to recreate a newly constructed past that answers the needs of the present. A digital heritage platform with AI-powered trip planning offers a partial solution by externalizing communal memory from oral tradition to searchable database, operationalizing Davis’s insight: the platform reconstructs the past in a form that serves present-day genealogical and touristic needs. A grandmother who remembers the family’s community of origin can anchor that knowledge in the database; her grandchildren can later retrieve it through surname search, even if the oral chain is broken. This does not replace lived memory but provides a durable supplement to it.

Muslim-Jewish shared heritage

Haddaji (2025) emphasizes the deep bonds between Moroccan Jews and their Muslim neighbors, noting that “the friendships and bonds of kinship that were forged have left an exceptional mark on the memory of Moroccan Jews, even at the cultural level, such as the shared pilgrimages to Jewish saints, music, poetry and literature.” Heritage tourism that includes cemetery visits and mellah exploration necessarily engages with this shared history. The Zyara trip planner, by contextualizing Jewish heritage within the broader Moroccan landscape, supports what Boumezzouzi (2020) describes as “a heritage of tolerance and coexistence between Jews and Muslims.” This is a narrative with considerable contemporary relevance. Ouaknine and Aharony

(2020) found that 58% of participants in Moroccan Facebook heritage communities cited “friendship and relations between communities” as a primary motivation for participation, and that, surprisingly, political matters and the Israeli-Arab conflict did not appear in the qualitative data, suggesting that shared heritage discussions create a space insulated from contemporary political tensions.

Limitations

Several limitations must be acknowledged. The Yahasra database, while the largest structured corpus of Moroccan Jewish burial records, covers 36 of an estimated several hundred Jewish cemeteries in Morocco, and its Chao1 analysis suggests that less than half of historical surname diversity has been captured. The trip planner currently covers only Marrakech and Safi, with expansion to additional communities dependent on database growth. The inter-community genetic distances reported by Ouaknine (2026) are limited to five Center/South communities; no Northern community met the sample threshold for pairwise analysis, which limits the planner’s ability to contextualize Northern heritage sites.

The AI trip planner is a prototype developed for the Hackathon Mémoire, Patrimoine, Innovation & Investissement (Université Cadi Ayyad, Marrakech, April 2026) and has not yet been evaluated with end users. The central claim of this paper, that AI-driven personalization transforms passive nostalgia into active heritage engagement, remains theoretical until validated empirically. A follow-up study is planned in which a controlled sample of diaspora tourists will use the Zyara trip planner to prepare and conduct heritage visits to Marrakech and Safi. The evaluation will employ pre- and post-visit questionnaires measuring perceived connection to heritage, satisfaction with itinerary personalization, and intention to return, compared with a control group using generic heritage tour itineraries. This user study will provide the empirical grounding that the current prototype-stage tool necessarily lacks.

The treatment of maternal surnames in the burial database constitutes a methodological limitation that affects the onomastic matching layer. The database records the surname as inscribed on the gravestone; for married women, this is typically the husband’s surname, and maiden names appear inconsistently (Ouaknine, 2026). This may cause the system to miss matches for families searching through the maternal line.

Conclusion

The Moroccan Jewish diaspora faces a narrowing window for heritage preservation. The material record is deteriorating, the generation with lived memory is aging, and the oral transmission chain is fraying. Haddaji (2025) has documented this erosion from the perspective of identity and memory. Ouaknine and Aharony (2020) and Ouaknine (2023) have provided empirical evidence that nostalgia drives heritage-oriented social network participation. Ouaknine (2026) has addressed it from the perspective of computational documentation and demographic analysis. This paper argues that the two approaches are complementary and that their convergence, through AI-powered tools like the Zyara trip planner, can transform passive nostalgia into active heritage engagement.

The key technical enablers are threefold: a structured burial database with sufficient coverage and demographic metadata; a phonetic normalization algorithm capable of bridging the multilingual transliteration landscape of Moroccan Jewish surnames; and an AI agent that translates database queries into personalized travel itineraries. Together, these components create a system in which a diaspora family can move from a surname to a cemetery to a journey, closing the gap between broken memory and lived reconnection.

We do not claim that technology can replace the emotional, spiritual, and communal dimensions of heritage, but we argue that it can provide the informational infrastructure without which those dimensions cannot be activated for the growing number of diaspora descendants who have lost the oral chain. As Haddaji (2025) notes, these descendants are “like a tree uprooted from its native soil.” The Zyara platform offers, if not the soil itself, then at least a map back to where the roots once grew.

Declarations

Declaration of Interest. The authors declare no competing interests. This research was supported in part by a Research Associate fellowship from the Digital Humanities and Social Sciences Hub (DHSS Hub) at the Open University of Israel. The funder had no role in the design of the study, the collection, analysis, or interpretation of data, or in the writing of this

manuscript. The Yahasra.org platform was developed and maintained independently by the first author.

Ethics Approval. This study is based exclusively on historical burial inscriptions, gravestone records, digitized archival registers, and published academic sources. No living human participants were involved, and no personal data from living individuals were collected or processed. Ethics approval was therefore not required.

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